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Comparative Analysis of Local and Lateral Stability of Plates as The Constraint Functions Within Optimization of Main Girder Box Section of the Bridge Crane

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Abstract: The paper considers the problem of optimization of the box section of the main girder of the bridge crane with rail placed above vertical plate. Criteria of strength, local and lateral stability of the girder were applied as the constraint functions. In addition, an influence of production technology on obtained optimization results is shown through comparative analysis. Reduction of girder mass is set as the objective function and the method of Lagrange multipliers was used as the methodology. The comparative optimization results show changes of the box section optimum geometric values due to Euro code or domestic standard appliance. The significant recommendations for crane designers were made upon the comparative analysis of optimization results and existing solutions.

Key words: bridge crane, optimization, strength, local stability of plates, lateral stability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The selection of the optimum shape and geometrical parameters of carrying structures, which influence the reduction of mass and costs of manufacturing, is the subject of research of many authors, regardless of whether they deal specifically with cranes or carrying structures in general ([1-6],[10-13]). This paper demonstrates an analytical method of optimization which gives the functional dependences of results that define the influence of some parameters on mass reduction more accurately. Within optimization of the main girder box section, permissible stress and permissible deflection as the constraint functions are used most often. Nevertheless, corresponding standards and regulations ([7-9], [14]) also define criteria of local and lateral stability as constraint functions. Therefore, they are taken into consideration through optimization here.

The paper shows the optimization of geometrical parameters of the bridge crane box girder cross section in case of rail placed above the vertical plate. Optimum parameters are defined for all constraint functions and comparative analysis is carried out. Obtained results give a significant contribution to bridge design of crane box girder.

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF THE OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

The task of optimization is to define geometrical parameters of the cross section of the girder as well as their mutual relations, which result in its minimum area. General mathematical formulation of optimization problem defined in this way is described in detail in [16]. As constraint functions in this optimization, the criteria of strength (1.1), lateral stability (1.2) and local stability (1.3) are used:

$$g_1 = \sigma_{r1} - \sigma_{k1} \leq 0, \quad (1.1)$$

$$g_2 = \sigma_{r2} - \sigma_{k2} \leq 0, \quad (1.2)$$

$$g_3 = \sigma_{r3} - \sigma_{k3} \leq 0, \quad (1.3)$$

where:

σ_{ri}, σ_{ki} - the calculation and permissible stresses for all three quoted criteria.

The Lagrange function is defined in the following way:

$$\Phi = A + \lambda_1 \cdot g_1 + \lambda_2 \cdot g_2 + \lambda_3 \cdot g_3, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial b} = 0; \frac{\partial A}{\partial b} + \lambda_1 \cdot \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial b} + \lambda_2 \cdot \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial b} + \lambda_3 \cdot \frac{\partial g_3}{\partial b} = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial h} = 0; \frac{\partial A}{\partial h} + \lambda_1 \cdot \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial h} + \lambda_2 \cdot \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial h} + \lambda_3 \cdot \frac{\partial g_3}{\partial h} = 0, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \lambda_i} = 0; \Rightarrow g_i = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \lambda_2} = 0; \Rightarrow g_2 = 0, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \lambda_i \cdot \left(\frac{\partial g_i}{\partial b} \cdot \frac{\partial A}{\partial h} - \frac{\partial g_i}{\partial h} \cdot \frac{\partial A}{\partial b} \right) = 0$$

Since $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \neq 0$, we get:

$$1. \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial b} \cdot \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial h} = \frac{\partial A}{\partial h} \cdot \frac{\partial g_1}{\partial b} \quad \wedge \quad g_1 = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$2. \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial b} \cdot \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial h} = \frac{\partial A}{\partial h} \cdot \frac{\partial g_2}{\partial b} \quad \wedge \quad g_2 = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$3. \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial b} \cdot \frac{\partial g_3}{\partial h} = \frac{\partial A}{\partial h} \cdot \frac{\partial g_3}{\partial b} \quad \wedge \quad g_3 = 0 \quad (6)$$

3. OBJECTIVE AND CONSTRAINT FUNCTIONS

3.1. OBJECTIVE FUNCTIONS

For this constraint functions, the objective function is the area of the cross section of the box girder [16], wherein the optimization parameters are (h, b) (Fig. 1), and the values

of wall thicknesses t_1 and t_2 were taken in accordance with the recommendations of crane manufacturers [15].

Fig. 1 The box section of the main girder of the bridge crane

The vector of the given parameters is:

$$\vec{x} = (M_{cv}, M_{ch}, Q, L, k_a, \dots) \quad (7)$$

where:

- M_{cv} and M_{ch} are the bending moments in the vertical and horizontal planes,
- Q - the load capacity of the crane
- L - the span of the crane,
- k_a - the dynamic coefficient of crane load in the horizontal plane, [9].

The objective function is:

$$A(h, b) = f(h, b) = \frac{2}{s} \cdot (e \cdot b \cdot h + h^2), \quad (8)$$

where: $e = t_1/t_2$ - the ratio between thicknesses of plates at the flange and at the web, $s = h/t_2$ - the ratio between the height and thickness of the plate at the web, $k = h/b$ - the ratio between the height and width of the girder.

Considering results in [16] geometric characteristics are:

$$I_x = \beta_x^2 \cdot h^2 \cdot A, \quad W_x = \alpha_x \cdot h \cdot A, \quad (9)$$

$$I_y = \beta_y^2 \cdot b^2 \cdot A; \quad W_y = \alpha_y \cdot b \cdot A, \quad (10)$$

$$S_{px} = \gamma_x \cdot h \cdot A, \quad (11)$$

$$\beta_x \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{k+3 \cdot e}{3 \cdot (e+k)}}, \quad \alpha_x \approx \frac{k+3 \cdot e}{6 \cdot (e+k)}. \quad (12)$$

$$\beta_y \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot k \cdot f^2 + e}{3 \cdot (e+k)}}, \quad \alpha_y \approx \frac{3 \cdot k \cdot f^2 + e}{6 \cdot (e+k)}. \quad (13)$$

$$\gamma_x \approx \frac{k+2 \cdot e}{8 \cdot (e+k)}. \quad (14)$$

4. CONSTRAINT FUNCTIONS

4.1.1. Strength criterion

According to strength criterion, the constraint function reads:

$$g_1(h, b) = \frac{M_{cv} + c \cdot A}{\alpha_x \cdot h \cdot A} + \frac{M_{ch} + k_a \cdot c \cdot A}{\alpha_y \cdot b \cdot A} - \sigma_{k1} \leq 0 \quad (15)$$

where:

$$\sigma_{k1} = f_y / \nu_1 - \text{permissible stresses from JUS,}$$

$$\sigma_{k1} = f_y / (\nu_1 \cdot \gamma_m) - \text{permissible stresses from Euro code,}$$

$\gamma_m = 1,1$ - the general resistance factor,

$\nu_1 = 1,5$ - the factored load coefficient for load case 1,

c - girder self weight coefficient.

With partial derivatives from equation (8)

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial b} = \frac{2}{s} \cdot e \cdot h; \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial h} = \frac{2}{s} \cdot (e \cdot b + 2 \cdot h); \quad (4.1)$$

put in (4), along with appropriate transformations, we get:

$$\frac{M_{cv} + c \cdot A}{M_{ch} + k_a \cdot c \cdot A} \approx \frac{M'_{cv}}{M'_{ch}}, \quad (16)$$

Fig. 3 presents relation (M'_{cv}/M'_{ch}) for general position of bridge crane load (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Loads of the main girder of the bridge crane

Fig. 3 Approximation of the equation (16)

a) The function M'_{cv}/M'_{ch}

b) The function M_{cv}/M_{ch} for $L = 25m$

c) The function M_{cv}/M_{ch} for $L = 10m$

Based on this, it is written:

$$\frac{M'_{cv}}{M'_{ch}} = \frac{1}{k_a} \cdot \frac{R}{R_h} = \frac{1}{k_a} \cdot c_1. \quad (17)$$

Member c_1 reads [11]:

$$c_1 = \frac{\psi \cdot Q + m_o + K \cdot Q^\alpha}{Q + m_o + K \cdot Q^\alpha}, \quad (18)$$

where: K - the coefficient of influence of the classification class on the mass of the trolley, ψ - the dynamic coefficient of the influence of load oscillation in the vertical plane, α - the coefficient of influence of the load mass on the mass of the trolley, m_o - the assumed mass of the trolley in the first approximation.

Using the relations (4.1), (16) and (17), the optimum value of relation k is obtained according to this criterion:

$$k_1 = \sqrt{\frac{e \cdot \alpha_y \cdot M'_{cv}}{\alpha_x \cdot M'_{ch}}} = \sqrt{\frac{e \cdot \alpha_y \cdot c_1}{\alpha_x \cdot k_a}}. \quad (19)$$

Using derived dependence, the objective function can be written in the following form:

$$A_1(h) \geq \frac{M_{cv}/\alpha_x + M_{ch}/\alpha_y \cdot k_1}{\sigma_{k1} \cdot h - c/\alpha_x - k_a \cdot c/\alpha_y \cdot k_1}. \quad (20)$$

4.1.2. The criterion of lateral stability

Testing of the box girder stability against lateral buckling was carried out in compliance with the Serbian standards [8]. Procedure of finding the optimum value of parameter k is explained in detail in [16], wherein the objective function according to criterion of lateral stability can be written in the following form:

$$A_2(h) \geq \frac{K_1 \cdot M_{cv} \cdot k_2^2 \cdot f(h) + K_2 \cdot M_{ch} \cdot k_2 \cdot h^2}{\sigma_{k2} \cdot h^3 - K_1 \cdot c \cdot k_2^2 \cdot f(h) - K_2 \cdot k_a \cdot c \cdot k_2 \cdot h^2}, \quad (21)$$

where: $K_1 = \frac{2 \cdot \gamma_x}{\beta_x^2 \cdot \beta_y^2}$, $K_2 = \frac{0,9}{\alpha_y}$ - constants,

$$f(h) = a \cdot m^2 + g \cdot m \cdot \beta_y \cdot \frac{h}{k_2} + d \cdot \beta_y^2 \cdot \frac{h^2}{k_2^2}. \quad (22)$$

4.1.3. The local stability of plates

The local stability testing of the flange and vertical plate was done in accordance with the standards (14). The flange plate has width b_1 and thickness t_1 (Fig. 4), the web plate above the longitudinal stiffener has length a , height h_1 and thickness t_2 , and the web plate under the longitudinal stiffener has length a , height h_2 and thickness t_2 .

In addition, testing of the flange plate segment subjected to the action of normal compressive stress in the x direction was carried out. Its dimensions are: length $a=2h$, width b_1 and thickness t_1 . This criterion is met if the local stability condition is fulfilled:

$$g_3(h,b) = \frac{M_{cv} + c \cdot A}{\alpha_x \cdot h \cdot A} + f \cdot \frac{M_{ch} + k_a \cdot c \cdot A}{\alpha_y \cdot b \cdot A} - \frac{\sigma_{k3}}{\nu_1} \leq 0, \quad (23)$$

where: $\sigma_{k3} = \kappa_x \cdot f_y / \gamma_m$ - critical stress, κ_x - a reduction factor.

Fig. 4 Flange and vertical plates

The reduction factor reads:

$$\kappa_x = c_e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_x} - \frac{0,22}{\lambda_x^2} \right) \leq 1 \text{ for } \lambda_x > 0,673, \quad (24)$$

$$\kappa_x = 1 \text{ for } \lambda_x \leq 0,673,$$

where: λ_x - the non-dimensional slenderness coefficient,

$$\lambda_x = \sqrt{\frac{f_{yk}}{K\sigma \cdot \sigma_e}}, \quad (25)$$

$$c_e = 1,25 - 0,12 \cdot \psi_e, c_e \leq 1,25 \quad (26)$$

ψ_e - the edge stress ratio of the plate, relative to the maximum compressive stress, $K\sigma$ - a buckling factor [16]. The reference stress σ_e reads:

$$\sigma_e = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot E}{12 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \cdot (t_1 / b_1)^2. \quad (27)$$

In the cross section I the vertical diaphragms are placed at the distance of $2h$, so that this ratio takes the value: $\alpha_e = a / b_1 = 2 \cdot h / (f \cdot b) > 1$.

Also, it is necessary to analyze coefficient ψ_e . It takes following value:

$$\psi_e = \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1} = \frac{\frac{c_1 \cdot \alpha_y}{k_a \cdot \alpha_x} - f \cdot k}{\frac{c_1 \cdot \alpha_y}{k_a \cdot \alpha_x} + f \cdot k}, \quad (28)$$

where:

$\nu_1 = 1,5$ - the factored load coefficient for load case 1,

σ_1, σ_2 - the stresses due to the factored load.

For average values, this ratio can also be approximately written by the expression

$$\psi_p \approx 0,83 - 0,06 \cdot k, \quad (28.1)$$

and with appropriate transformation it can be obtained:

$$c_p \approx 1,15 + 0,0072 \cdot k, \quad (26.1)$$

$$K\sigma_p = \frac{8,2}{1,88 - 0,06 \cdot k}, \quad (29)$$

$$\sigma_e = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot E}{12 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \cdot \left(\frac{e \cdot k}{s \cdot f} \right)^2, \quad (27.1)$$

$$\lambda_{sp} \approx \frac{K\sigma}{\sqrt{K\sigma_p}} \cdot \frac{s \cdot f}{e \cdot k}. \quad (25.1)$$

In Fig. 6 it is shown that the factor κ_x takes value 1, for classification class 2m/M5 and girder material S235JRG2.

Fig. 6 Buckling coefficient

Having the method of Lagrange multipliers applied for criterion of lateral stability, using the corresponding partial derivatives (6) and relations (8) and (23), we get:

$$k_3 = \sqrt{\frac{e \cdot \alpha_y \cdot c_1}{f \cdot \alpha_x \cdot k_a}} \quad (30)$$

From this expression, we can get the optimum value of the parameter k for the flange plate. Using the obtained dependencies from the constraint function according to this criterion, the constraint function reads:

$$A_3(h) \geq \frac{M_{cv} / \alpha_x + f \cdot M_{ch} / \alpha_y \cdot k_3}{\sigma_{k_3} \cdot h - c / \alpha_x - f \cdot k_a \cdot c / \alpha_y \cdot k_3} \quad (31)$$

Local stability testing of the vertical plate was done in areas 1 and 2 (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Vertical plate

Besides the normal stresses in x direction, there is also normal stress in y direction, due to the action of wheel pressure.

The case when, besides vertical stiffeners at midspan, a row of horizontal stiffeners is also placed at the distance of $(0,25 \div 0,33) \cdot h$, was studied. The areas 1 and 2 were analyzed.

Area 1: This criterion is met if the local stability condition is fulfilled:

$$\left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd1,x}|}{f_{b,Rd1,x}} \right)^{e_{1x}} + \left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd1,y}|}{f_{b,Rd1,y}} \right)^{e_{1y}} - (\kappa_{1x} \cdot \kappa_{1y})^6 \cdot \left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd1,x} \cdot \sigma_{Sd1,y}|}{f_{b,Rd1,x} \cdot f_{b,Rd1,y}} \right) \leq 1 \quad (32)$$

Stresses in x and y direction at point 1, the compressive stress limits and corresponding coefficients are as follows:

$$|\sigma_{Sd1,x}| = V_1 \cdot \left(\frac{M_{cv} + c \cdot A}{\alpha_x \cdot h \cdot A} + f \cdot \frac{M_{ch} + k_a \cdot c \cdot A}{\alpha_y \cdot b \cdot A} \right)$$

$$|\sigma_{Sd1,y}| = V_1 \cdot \frac{\gamma \cdot F_1}{t_2 \cdot l_{1r}}$$

$$f_{b,Rd1,x} = \kappa_{1x} \cdot f_y / \gamma_m, \quad f_{b,Rd1,y} = \kappa_{1y} \cdot f_y / \gamma_m$$

$$e_{1x} = 1 + \kappa_{1x}^4, \quad e_{1y} = 1 + \kappa_{1y}^4$$

A reference stress σ_{1e} reads:

$$\sigma_{1e} = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot E}{12 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \cdot \left(\frac{t_2}{h_1} \right)^2 = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot E}{12 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \cdot \left(\frac{4}{s} \right)^2 \quad (33)$$

Since there is:

$$\psi_{1p} \approx 0,54 + 0,015 \cdot k \quad (34)$$

it can be noted:

$$K\sigma_{1p} = \frac{8,2}{1,59 + 0,015 \cdot k} \quad (35)$$

$$\lambda_{1,sp} \approx \frac{Ko}{\sqrt{K\sigma_{1p}}} \cdot \frac{s}{4} \quad (36)$$

Fig. 8 shows that the value of coefficient is $\kappa_{1x} = 1$, wherein classification class is 2 and material is S235JRG2. Increasing the slenderness s leads to some lower values.

Fig. 8 Buckling coefficient

A similar analysis is for the load in y direction, where:

F_1 - the highest wheel pressure, $l_{1r} = 12,15 + 1,4 \cdot e$ - effective distribution length [16], c_{1r} - the width of transverse load distribution, κ_{1y} - a reduction factor for area 1:

$$\kappa_{1y} = 1,13 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{1y}} - \frac{0,22}{\lambda_{1y}^2} \right) \leq 1 \quad \text{for } \lambda_{1y} > 0,831, \quad (37)$$

$$\kappa_{1y} = 1 \quad \text{for } \lambda_{1y} \leq 0,831,$$

$$\lambda_{1y} = \frac{Ko}{\sqrt{K\sigma_{1y}} \cdot a / c_{1r}} \cdot \frac{s}{4} \quad (38)$$

$$K\sigma_{1y} \approx 0,5 \quad [16].$$

Fig. 9 shows that for average and expected parameters values, the value of coefficient is $\kappa_{1y} = 1$, wherein classification class is 2 and material is S235JRG2.

Fig. 9 Buckling coefficient

For these parameters values, the relation (34) is:

$$\sqrt{|\sigma_{Sd1,x}|^2 + |\sigma_{Sd1,y}|^2} - |\sigma_{Sd1,x} \cdot \sigma_{Sd1,y}| \leq f_y / \gamma_m \quad (39)$$

This is valid if fulfilled:

$|\sigma_{Sd1,x}| \geq |\sigma_{Sd1,y}|$, or the left side must be greater then the right side, $f_l(L) \geq f_d(L)$ - Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 The results of critical stress analysis in x and y directions

A similar procedure is applied for area 2.

$$\left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd2,x}|}{f_{b,Rd2,x}} \right)^{e_{2x}} + \left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd2,y}|}{f_{b,Rd2,y}} \right)^{e_{2y}} - (\kappa_{2x} \cdot \kappa_{2y})^6 \cdot \left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd2,x} \cdot \sigma_{Sd2,y}|}{f_{b,Rd2,x} \cdot f_{b,Rd2,y}} \right) \leq 1, \quad (40)$$

Stresses in x and y direction at point 2, the compressive stress limits and corresponding coefficients are as follows:

$$|\sigma_{Sd2,x}| = v_1 \cdot \left(\frac{M_{cv} + c \cdot A}{2 \cdot \alpha_x \cdot h \cdot A} + f \cdot \frac{M_{ch} + k_a \cdot c \cdot A}{\alpha_y \cdot b \cdot A} \right),$$

$$|\sigma_{Sd2,y}| = v_1 \cdot \frac{\gamma \cdot F_1}{t_2 \cdot l_{2r}},$$

$$f_{b,Rd2,x} = \kappa_{2x} \cdot f_y / \gamma_m, \quad f_{b,Rd2,y} = \kappa_{2y} \cdot f_y / \gamma_m,$$

$$e_{2x} = 1 + \kappa_{2x}^4, \quad e_{2y} = 1 + \kappa_{2y}^4.$$

A reference stress σ_{2e} reads:

$$\sigma_{2e} = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot E}{12 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \cdot \left(\frac{t_2}{h_2} \right)^2 = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot E}{12 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \cdot \left(\frac{4}{3 \cdot s} \right)^2. \quad (41)$$

Since there is

$$\psi_{2p} \approx -(0,6 + 0,01 \cdot k), \quad (42)$$

it can be noted:

$$K\sigma_{2p} = 15,1 + 1,8 \cdot k + 0,0978 \cdot k^2, \quad (43)$$

$$\lambda_{2sp} \approx \frac{Ko}{\sqrt{K\sigma_{2p}}} \cdot (3 \cdot s / 4). \quad (44)$$

Fig. 11 shows changes in value of the coefficient κ_{2x} , wherein classification class is 2 and material is S235JRG2. Increasing the slenderness s leads to some lower values.

Fig. 11 Buckling coefficient

Further on, load in y direction is analyzed, where:

$l_{2r} = 12,15 + 2 \cdot e \cdot h / s + h / 2$ - the effective distribution length [14], κ_{2y} - a reduction factor for area 2,

$K\sigma_{2y} \approx 1,2$ - buckling coefficient [14], c_{2r} - the width over which the transverse load is distributed

$$\lambda_{12} = \frac{Ko}{\sqrt{K\sigma_{2y} \cdot a / c_{2r}}} \cdot \frac{3 \cdot s}{4}, \quad (45)$$

Fig. 12 shows that for average and expected parameters values, the value of coefficient κ_{2y} is changing, wherein classification class is 2 and material is S235JRG2.

Fig. 12 Buckling coefficient

For such obtained values, the relation (34.2) becomes:

$$\left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd2,x}|}{f_{b,Rd2,x}} \right)^{e_{2x}} + \left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd2,y}|}{f_{b,Rd2,y}} \right)^{e_{2y}} \leq 1. \quad (46)$$

To do analysis, the ratio between the maximum compressive stress in this area and the compressive stress that occurred.

$$|\sigma_{Sd2,x}| = \psi_2 \cdot |\sigma_{Sd,max,x}| \approx (0,52 + 0,009 \cdot k) \cdot |\sigma_{Sd,max,x}|$$

Now, (34.2.1) reads:

$$\left(\psi_2 / \kappa_{2x} \right)^{1 + \kappa_{2x}^4} + \left(\frac{|\sigma_{Sd2,y}|}{\gamma_m / (\kappa_{2y} \cdot f_y)} \right)^{1 + \kappa_{2y}^4} \leq 1. \quad (47)$$

Fig. 13 shows that for average parameters values and with load and internal width changing, this relation varies, wherein it was taken $s = 160$.

Fig. 13 The analysis results

Based on all mentioned above, it is possible to adopt such parameters that make the local stability criterion fulfilled. The area 1 is critical for the investigation of vertical plates local stability, while the highest stress is analogous to flange plate stress. Factors κ_x and κ_{1x} take value 1 for expected values of relation k and slenderness s . According to this criterion, the same curve or constraint (g_3) is taken into account, as obtained in previous expression. In addition, according to this criterion, the optimal value for k is determined out of expression (30), just as flange plate local stability. Relation (31) defines the objective function.

5. NUMERICAL REPRESENTATION OF THE OBTAINED RESULTS

Using the expressions (19), (22) and (30), the optimum value of the parameter k , according to considered criteria, is obtained. Optimum values of the parameter k , as a function of the member e , are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

e	1,2	1,3	1,4	1,5
k_1	3,90	4,00	4,10	4,25
k_2	3,35	3,33	3,31	3,30
k_3	4,20	4,30	4,40	4,55

The expression (20) represents the objective function obtained from the constraint function according to the criterion of lateral stability and together with the objective function (8) can be graphically represented. Expression (20) is presented with dashed curve, while expression (8) is presented by continuous curve (Figures 14 and 15). It can be seen how the position of the intersection point changes depending on the selection of material according to domestic standard (Fig. 14) or Euro code (Fig. 15), wherein adopted values are $L=20 m$ and $Q=12.5 t$.

Fig. 14 Optimum values of the girder height and the objective function according to strength criterion and JUS standard
a) S235JRG2 b) S275JR c) S355JR

Fig. 15 Optimum values of the girder height and the objective function according to strength criterion and Euro code
a) S235JRG2 b) S275JR c) S355JR

Ref. [16] shows this intersection point position changing according to lateral stability criterion.

The expression (31) represents the objective function obtained from the constraint function according to the criterion of local stability and together with the objective function (8) can be graphically presented in the same manner (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16 Optimum values of the girder height and the objective function according to local stability criterion
a) S235JRG2 b) S275JR c) S355JR

For starting the analysis, values in the middle of the range can be taken, so that for S235JRG2 it is $s = 210$, while for S355JR $s = 170$. Other parameters values, in this phase, are:

$$e = 1,33, f = 0,85, \psi = 1,15, k_a = 0,1, \\ e_k = 2,3m, G_k = 15kN.$$

The analysis was performed for the classification class 2m/M5, which is the most frequent in practice. The following values are valid for it:

$$\gamma = 1,05, \alpha = 1,20, K = 0,08, m_o = 1,20.$$

Also: Serbian crane manufacturers recommend that the minimum value of the width b_1 should be $b_1 > 30cm$, wherefrom it is obtained that

$$k \leq f \cdot h / 30, \quad (48)$$

while foreign manufacturers recommend $b_1 > 20cm$:

$$k \leq f \cdot h / 20. \quad (49)$$

If we make equal expression (8) with (19), (22) and (30), the dependence of the parameter k , according to the considered criteria, is obtained

$$k_1 = F(s, e, h, M_{cv}, M_{ch}, \alpha_x, \alpha_y, f_y, k_a), \quad (50)$$

$$k_2 = F(s, e, h, K_1, K_2, M_{cv}, M_{ch}, \sigma_{k2}, c, k_a), \quad (51)$$

$$k_3 = F(s, e, f, h, Q, M_{cv}, M_{ch}, \alpha_x, \alpha_y, k_a, f_y), \quad (53)$$

whereby dependence (50) will be presented for domestic standard (50.1) and Euro code (50.2) separately.

The following Figures present optimum geometric parameters values that are obtained for characteristic load capacities and spans of double-girder bridge cranes.

It can be seen that both domestic and Euro code standard have strength for optimum criterion for studied cases.

Fig. 17 Multicriteria determination of the optimum value of the parameter k for the crane span $L=12m$ and the carrying capacity $Q = 5t$

Fig. 18 Multicriteria determination of the optimum value of the parameter k for the crane span $L=12m$ and the carrying capacity $Q = 16t$

Fig. 19 Multicriteria determination of the optimum value of the parameter k for the crane span $L=20m$ and the carrying capacity $Q = 5t$

Fig. 20 Multicriteria determination of the optimum value of the parameter k for the crane span $L=20m$ and the carrying capacity $Q = 16t$

6. CONCLUSION

The paper presented analytical expressions that define optimum dimensions of the main girder box section of the bridge crane, wherein the rail is placed above the vertical plate. The analysis used the method of Lagrange

multipliers, where strength, lateral and local stability criteria were used as constraint functions. Optimum cross section area can be calculated out of geometric parameters defined by analytical forms. The obtained results were compared in cases of different constraint functions, so procedure for finding the unique solution is set. Comparative analysis encompasses also the influence of manufacturing technology on the optimum solution. This procedure enables quick and efficient determination of geometric parameters optimum values, according to critical function and for input data and given constraints. According to Euro code, there exists a significant congruence between curves of strength and local stability of plates. In addition, it can be seen that the obtained optimum values are significantly affected by manufacturing technology.

Appliance of the method of Lagrange multipliers is fully justified because it enabled finding the analytical forms of optimization. They are used for judging about certain influences and making some further studies about mass reduction.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Farkas J (1984) *Optimum design of metal structures*. Akademiai KIADO, Budapest
- [2] Farkas J (1986) *Economy of Higher-Strength Steels in Overhead Travelling Cranes with Double-Box Girders*. *J. Construct. Steel Research* 6: 285-301
- [3] Farkas J, Jármai K (1997) *Analysis and optimum design of metal structures*. Balkema, Rotterdam
- [4] Farkas J, Jármai K, Snyman JA (2010) *Global minimum cost design of a welded square stiffened plate supported at four corners*. *Struct Multidisc Optim* 40:477–489
- [5] Gašić M, Savković M, Bulatović R, Petrović R (2011) *Optimization of a pentagonal cross section of the truck crane boom using Lagrange's multipliers and differential evolution algorithm*. *Meccanica*. 46(2011) 4:845-853
- [6] Gašić M, Savković M, Bulatović R (2011b) *Optimization of trapezoidal cross section of the truck crane boom by Lagrange's multipliers and by differential evolution algorithm (DE)*. *Strojniški vestnik – Journal of Mechanical Engineering* 57(2011) 4:304-312
- [7] JUS M.D1.050 (1968) *Standards for cranes*. The Yugoslav Institute for Standardization (Standardi za dizalice. Jugoslovenski zavod za standardizaciju), Belgrade
- [8] JUS U.E7. (1986) *Standards for calculation of steel carrying structures*. The Yugoslav Institute for Standardization (Standardi za proračun nosećih čeličnih konstrukcija. Jugoslovenski zavod za standardizaciju), Belgrade
- [9] Ostrić D, Tošić S (2005) *Cranes (Dizalice)*. Institute for Mechanization of the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of the University in Belgrade (Institut za mehanizaciju Mašinskog fakulteta Univerziteta u Beogradu), Belgrade
- [10] Pinca BC, Tirian OG, Socalici VA, Ardeleadn DE (2009) *Dimensional optimization for the strength structure of a traveling crane*. *WSEAS Transactions on Applied and heoretical Mechanics* 4 (4), pp 147:156
- [11] Pinca BC, Tirian OG, Josan A, Chete G (2009) *Quantitative and qualitative study on the state of stresses and strains of the strength structure of a crane bridge*. *WSEAS Transactions on Applied and heoretical Mechanics* 5 (4), pp 231:241
- [12] Savković M (2005) *Optimization of Complex Cross Sections of Structures of Autocrane Booms (Optimizacija složenih poprečnih preseka konstrukcija strele autodizalice)*. (IMK -14- Istraživanje i razvoj) 20-21(1) pp 41:45
- [13] Selmic R, Cvetkovic R, Mijailovic R (2006) *Optimization of crosssection in structures, monograph*. The Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade
- [14] prEN 13001-3-1 (2010) *Cranes - General Design - Part 3-1: Limit States and proof competence of steel structure*, EUROPEAN COMMITTEE FOR STANDARDIZATION
- [15] *Catalogues (1996) and as-built projects of Serbian crane manufacturers*. IMK 14 Oct., MIN, ILR (Katalozi i projekti izvedenog stanja Srpskih proizvođača dizalica IMK 14 Oktobar, MIN, ILR)
- [16] Pavlović G, Savković M, Zdravković N (2011) *Optimizacija kutijastog poprečnog preseka glavnog nosača mosne dizalice prema kriterijumu bočne stabilnosti (Optimization of the box section of the main girder of the bridge crane the criterion of lateral stability)*. IMK -14- Istraživanje i razvoj br. 41 (4/2011) pp 1:8